

1 **Novel engineered high performance sugar beetroot 2D nanoplatelet-cementitious**
2 **composites**

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14

15 **Abstract**

16 In this paper, we show for the first time that environmentally friendly nanoplatelets synthesized
17 from sugar beetroot waste with surface area and hydroxyl functional groups similar to those of
18 graphene oxide (GO) can be used to significantly enhance the performance of cementitious
19 composites. A comprehensive experimental and numerical simulation study was carried out to
20 examine the performance of the bio waste-derived 2D nanoplatelets (BNP) in cementitious
21 composites. The experimental results revealed that the addition of BNPs decreased the workability
22 of the cement pastes due to their high surface area and dominant hydrophilic functional groups.
23 The experimental results also revealed that the BNP sheets altered the morphology of the hydration
24 phases of the cementitious composites. At 0.20-wt%, the BNP sheets increased the content of the
25 C-S-H gels. At higher concentrations (i.e., 0.40-wt% and 0.60-wt%), however, the BNP sheets
26 increased the content of the calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)₂) products and altered their sizes and
27 morphologies.

28 The flexural results demonstrated that the 0.20-wt% BNPs produced the highest flexural strength
29 and modulus elasticity and they were increased by 80% and 200%, respectively. The numerical
30 simulations were in good agreement with the fracture test results. Both results showed that the
31 0.20-wt% BNPs optimal concentration significantly enhanced the fracture properties of the

32 cementitious composite and produced mixed mode crack propagation as a failure mode compared
33 to Mode I crack propagation for the plain cementitious composite due to combined crack bridging
34 and crack deflection toughening mechanisms. Because of this, the fracture energy and the fracture
35 toughness were increased by about 88% and 106%, respectively.

36 **1. Introduction**

37 A great deal of research efforts has been devoted to improving the performance of cementitious
38 composites using different nanoscale additives. Such additives offer tremendous promise for a
39 wide range of uses in cementitious materials that could result in sustainable and high performance
40 concrete structures with intelligence and multifunctional capabilities [1, 2]. For example,
41 cementitious composites incorporating reactive nanoparticles such as nano-SiO₂ [3,4], nano-TiO₂
42 [5, 6] and nano-CaCO₃ [7, 8] were found to exhibit improved mechanical properties and durability
43 characteristics. This is because the high specific area of nanoparticles accelerates the hydration of
44 cement, resulting in more Calcium Silicate Hydrate (C-S-H) gels. Furthermore, due to their small
45 particle size, the nanoparticles tend to act as fillers, which results in a denser microstructure.
46 However, these reactive nanoparticles tend to agglomerate at high concentrations and, due to their
47 low aspect ratios, they cannot arrest the propagation of cracks, thereby are unable to enhance the
48 fracture properties of cementitious composites [9].

49 A significant body of research has demonstrated the benefits of adding carbonaceous nano-
50 additives such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs), carbon nanofibers (NFs) and graphene oxide (GO) to
51 cementitious materials. However, CNTs and NFs were shown to provide limited improvements
52 in the mechanical properties due to their agglomeration and lack of chemical and mechanical
53 bonding with the cement composite matrix [10, 11]. The two dimensional (2D) GO is being
54 considered as an ideal candidate for reinforcing cementitious composites due to its distinctive

55 properties such as large specific area, excellent mechanical properties and high dispersibility in
56 water due to hydroxyl functional groups on its surface [12]. Studies reported that GO accelerates
57 the hydration of cement and, regulate the growth and morphology of the hydration phases, leading
58 to improvement in the mechanical properties of GO composites [13-15]. Studies also reported that
59 GO influences pore volume distribution in cementitious materials [16]. It was shown that GO
60 reduces the capillary pores and fills the micropores in the cement matrix [17]. Because of its large
61 specific area, GO was found to bridge microcracks, thereby enhancing the stiffness and the fracture
62 resistance of the cement matrix [18]. However, large-scale production of nano-SiO₂ nano-TiO₂,
63 nano-CaCO₃, CNTs, NFs and GO and their applications in cementitious materials have been
64 hampered by the high costs, un-scalability, complex manufacturing processes and, environmental,
65 health and safety risk issues.

66 In this paper, we investigate for the first time the performance of cementitious composites
67 containing novel and environmentally friendly low-cost 2D BNP sheets. The BNP sheets were
68 produced from renewable materials such as sugar beetroot waste and resemble GO in terms of
69 large specific area, excellent mechanical properties and hydroxyl functional groups with excellent
70 dispersibility in water. The effect of different BNP concentrations on the workability, hydration
71 phases, microstructure and mechanical properties was examined. The cracking behavior and the
72 failure mode of the BNP cementitious composites were also examined and validated using
73 numerical modelling.

74 **2. Experimental Program**

75 *2.1 Preparation of BNPs*

76 The BNP sheets were produced and supplied by our industrial partner Cellucomp Ltd, UK. The
77 BNP sheets were synthesized from sugar beetroot waste recovered from existing industrial

78 processes. The isolation of BNPs from sugar beetroot pulp is detailed in [19]. In summary, this
79 process involves alkali treatment of recovered sugar beetroot pulp with 0.5M of potassium
80 hydroxide (KOH) to extract the hemicellulose and pectin from the cells. The resulting mixture
81 was heated to 90°C for 5 hours and homogenized for 1 hour with a rotating mixer at rates between
82 11 and 30 m/s. This homogenization process separates the cells along the line of the middle lamella
83 and breaks the separated cells into BNP sheets with about. The mixture was then filtered to remove
84 the dissolved materials. Finally, a nonionic surfactant (SpanTM from Croda PLC, UK) was added
85 to the BNP paste to coat the surface of the platelets to reduce aggregation thereby allowing BNPs
86 to be readily dispersed in aqueous solutions [24].

87 *2.2. Preparation of BNP cement pastes*

88 Portland cement (OPC) type CEM I 52.5N was used to prepare the cementitious composites with
89 a water-to-cement ratio of 0.35. Commercially available superplasticizer (Glenium 51) was used
90 at a concentration of 1-wt% to enhance the workability of the cement pastes. The cement pastes
91 were modified with BNPs at concentrations of 0.20, 0.40 and 0.60-wt%. The BNPs were first
92 added to the required water and superplasticizer, followed by mild sonication for 30 min using a
93 probe sonicator. The resulting suspension was then blended with the cement and mixed for 7 min.
94 For each BNP loading, 24 prisms (40 mm× 40 mm× 160 mm) were prepared to determine the
95 mechanical and fracture properties of the cementitious composites. The prisms were demolded
96 after 24 hrs then left to cure in water at a temperature of 21 °C for 7, 14 and 28 days.

97 *2.3. Characterization of BNPs*

98 Optical microscopy and ultraviolet-visible spectrophotometer were employed to examine the
99 dispersion properties and stability of BNPs at sonication times of 30, 50 and 100 min. Scanning
100 electron microscopy with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM/EDX) and X-ray diffraction

101 (XRD) were used to determine the chemical composition, morphology and microstructure of the
102 BNP sheets. The Fourier transformed infrared (FTIR) spectrum was measured with an Exoscan
103 4100 FTIR Spectrometer in the range of 500–5000 cm^{-1} and was used to analyze the BNP sheets
104 and identify their functional groups. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was carried to study the
105 thermal stability of BNPs under temperatures between 25 and 1100°C at a rate of 10 °C/min in
106 nitrogen (N₂).

107 *2.4. Measurement of workability*

108 The effect of the BNP sheets on the workability of the cement pastes was assessed. A mini-slump
109 cone with a top diameter of 70 mm, a bottom diameter of 100 mm and a height of 60 mm was
110 employed in this slump test. The average slump was based on three measurements.

111 *2.5. Characterization of hydration and microstructure BNP cementitious composites*

112 Samples were collected from the fractured flexural prisms at 7, 14 and 28 days to examine the
113 effect of BNP concentration on the hydration and microstructure of the cementitious composites.
114 TGA measurements were performed to estimate the degree of hydration (DOH) and the content of
115 Ca(OH)₂. In this experiment, the samples were heated from 25 to 1100 °C at a rate of 10 °C/min
116 under nitrogen (N₂). In addition, TGA measurements were performed on BNPs and cement
117 particles for correction purposes [20]. XRD analysis was carried out to further investigate the
118 DOH and determine the crystallinity of the hydration phases. SEM/EDX was employed to carry
119 out elemental analysis on the chemical composition of the cementitious composites and investigate
120 their microstructure characteristics such as distribution of BNPs and crack bridging mechanism.
121 Transition electron microscopy (TEM) analysis was also conducted to study the microstructure
122 alteration processes associated with the addition of BNPs.

123

124 *2.6. Mechanical and fracture characterization of BNP cement composites*

125 As shown in Figs. 1a and 2a, four-point bending tests were conducted on 48 cementitious
126 composite prisms (40 mm ×40 mm ×160 mm) (12 prisms per BNP concentration) under
127 displacement control with a rate of 0.1 mm/min. The flexural strength and modulus of elasticity of
128 the prisms were determined. Additionally, 48 cementitious prisms (40 mm ×40 mm ×160 mm)
129 equipped with a notch (3 mm x 16 mm) at the mid-span were subjected to a three-point bending
130 test to evaluate the effect of BNPs on the fracture resistance of the prisms (Fig. 1b). The three-
131 point bending tests were also carried out under displacement control with a rate of 0.03 mm/min.
132 The crack mouth opening displacement (CMOD) was measured with a video gaugeTM acquired
133 from Imetrum LTd. The video gauge system consisted of two lenses, an iMetrum controller and
134 a data acquisition system. As can be seen in Fig. 2b, five lines of 6 black dots with a dot diameter
135 of 4 mm and a center-to- center spacing of 5 mm were printed on the surface of the prisms around
136 the notch to define the region where the displacement is measured. The lenses were placed 1.5 m
137 away from the surface of the prisms (Fig. 2c). During testing, the positions of the dots were
138 continuously monitored by the lenses (Fig. 2c), and recorded along with the load. Both load and
139 positions were recorded at a frequency of 15 Hz. The CMOD was obtained by monitoring the
140 horizontal displacement between the two dots adjacent to the mouth of the crack as shown in Fig.
141 1b. The load vs CMOD, and the calculated fracture energy and fracture toughness were employed
142 to quantify the contribution of BNP to the fracture resistance of the cementitious composites.

143 **3. Results and discussion**

144 *3.1. Characterization of BNP sheets*

145 The chemical components of the BNP sheets obtained from the EDX elemental analysis are given
146 in Table 1. As indicated in this table, the BNPs sheets contain mostly carbon, oxygen and

147 hydrogen. The main chemical components are carbon 47.61% and oxygen 46.91%. The BNP
148 sheets contain some sodium and chloride impurities as a result of their chemical treatments. The
149 XRD pattern of the BNP sheets is shown in Fig. 3. As can be seen, the sheets exhibit two main
150 peaks at $2\theta = 15$ and 22 , which represents the structure of cellulose. The XRD pattern suggests
151 that the structure of the BNP sheets can be divided into two regions. The narrow peak at $2\theta = 15$
152 represents the crystalline region of BNPs with a surface (110) plane. This surface (110) plane is
153 hydrophilic in nature due to the exposure to a large number of hydroxyl (OH) groups, thus, has a
154 good dispersion in water [21]. The somewhat broad peak at $2\theta = 22.5$ with surface (200) plane
155 indicates the presence of crystalline and amorphous regions of BNPs. The amorphous region is
156 associated with the amorphous lignin and hemicellulose components of BNPs. The crystalline
157 region is highly hydrophobic because of the existence of C-H moieties [21]. The crystallinity
158 index (CI) of BNPs was calculated using the following equation [21]:

$$159 \quad CI (\%) = 100 \times \frac{I_{002} - I_{am}}{I_{002}} \quad (1)$$

160 where I_{002} is the intensity of the XRD peak at $2\theta = 22.5$ and plane (200); I_{am} is the intensity of the
161 amorphous cellulose between the planes (200) and (110) at $2\theta = 18$. The calculated average CI
162 was about 64% which indicates high tensile strength and stiffness of the BNP sheets [21]. As a
163 result, the proposed BNP sheets are good candidate materials for reinforcing cementitious
164 composites. The FTIR spectrum of BNPs shown in Fig. 4 is similar to that reported by Li et al.
165 [21]. This figure shows that the absorption in the 3600 cm^{-1} - 3000 cm^{-1} region is the result of the
166 vibrational stretching bands of hydrogen bonded hydroxyl groups which indicates the hydrophilic
167 nature of the BNP sheets [21]. The pronounced peak at 2900 cm^{-1} is attributed to the stretching
168 vibration of saturated C-H in cellulose [21] and the peak at 1030 cm^{-1} is associated with the

169 bending vibration of the absorbed water molecules [21]. Figure 4 shows that asymmetric and
170 symmetric bending vibration bands exist at 1371 cm^{-1} and 1443 cm^{-1} [21].

171 The TGA/DTA results shown in Fig. 5 illustrate the thermal stability of BNPs. As depicted, the
172 BNP sheets exhibit a small mass loss when heated from 25 to 200°C due to the evaporation of
173 water content. A significant mass loss is observed between 200 and 700°C as a consequence of
174 elimination of hydroxyl groups and decomposition of the carbon chains [21]. The mass loss
175 remains constant at temperatures between 700 and 1100°C . The DTA spectrum shows a sharp
176 peak at a temperature of about 260°C due to the dehydration of BNP sheets and a broad peak at
177 about 500°C due to the decomposition of the BNP sheets. Overall, the BNP sheets exhibit a good
178 thermal stability in the temperature range of 25 to 100°C , which is the range in which cementitious
179 composites are typically operating.

180 Figure shows a typical micrograph of the BNP sheets, which indicates that the BNP sheets have a
181 wrinkled texture resulting from the treatment of the sugar beetroot. This texture typically consists
182 of crumpled and, stacked and overlapped thin sheets. This morphology enables the BNP sheets to
183 interact mechanically with cement matrix, thus significantly enhancing the overall mechanical
184 properties of the BNP composites [17]. It can be seen from Fig. 6 that the BNP sheets are
185 composed of randomly oriented staked nanofibers with a diameter of about 10 nm. It worth
186 mentioning that it was not possible to measure the dimensions of the BNP sheets, however,
187 according to the supplier, the average diameter of the flakes is about $50\text{ }\mu\text{m}$.

188 *3.2. Colloidal properties and stability of BNP aqueous solutions*

189 The colloidal properties and stability of the BNP aqueous suspensions were determined in terms
190 of state of aggregation and microscale dispersion in aqueous solutions. Figure 7b depicts a typical

191 optical microscope image of the prepared BNP aqueous suspensions shown in Fig. 7a. As can be
192 seen, the BNP sheets seem to be uniformly dispersed without agglomeration. Figure 8 shows the
193 UV-vis spectroscopy spectra of the BNP aqueous solution as a function of sonication time. As
194 shown, the absorbance of the BNP sheets exhibits a maximum between 300 and 320 nm at all
195 sonication times. As the sonication time increases, the area under the spectrum lines representing
196 the absorbance increases as well, resulting in highly dispersed BNP sheets in water. It is worth
197 noting that the optical microscope image and absorbance spectra remained unchanged after 1 year,
198 thus indicating good stability of the BNP aqueous solutions.

199 *3.3. Influence of BNP on the workability of cement pastes*

200 Figure 9 shows the effect of the BNP sheets on the workability of the cement pastes. As can be
201 seen, the addition of 0.20-wt% BNPs did not affect the slump of the cement paste, however, the
202 addition of 0.40-wt% BNPs and 0.60-wt% BNPs leads to a reduction in the slump of approximately
203 65% and 74%, respectively, compared to the control mix. The slump decreases as the content of
204 BNPs increases, which indicates that the slump loss is proportional to the content of BNPs. This
205 is attributed to the high hydrophilicity and large specific area of the BNP sheets, thereby requiring
206 extra water to wet their surface. This reduces the free water content in the cement pastes thereby
207 reducing their workability. This is consistent with previous studies on cementitious materials
208 containing GO sheets [22]. The workability of the cement pastes can be tuned by adding water
209 reducing admixtures to promote the electrostatic repulsions between the cement particles and the
210 BNP sheets.

211 *3.4. Influence of BNPs on the degree of hydration of cementitious composites*

212 The TGA results in terms of weight loss and derivative of the weight loss (DTA) are presented in
213 Fig. 10 for the cementitious composites. In this figure, the percentage of the weight loss gradually

214 decreases as the temperature increases and the inflections in the DTA represent the decomposition
215 of specific phases of the cement paste composites. The TGA/DTA provides insight into the
216 chemical reaction mechanisms in cementitious materials during heating. During this test, it was
217 observed that C-S-H and carboaluminate phases lose their bound water in the temperature range
218 180-300 °C; the dehydroxylation of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ takes place in the temperature range 430-480°C and
219 the decarbonation of calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) occurs in the temperature range 600–780°C [28].
220 From Fig. 10, it can be observed that the mass loss of the cementitious composites decreases with
221 increasing BNP concentration. This is due to the increase of the high density C-S-H content and
222 the creation of new intercalated BNP/C-S-H nanocomposites with higher density. This is
223 consistent with Rehman et al. [23] findings where they have shown that the decrease in the mass
224 loss of GO cementitious composites is attributed to both the bonding of C-S-H with the GO sheets
225 and the increase of the C-S-H content. In this case, the GO sheets tend to increase the amount of
226 C-S-H product, thereby filling the pores in the matrix resulting in less amount of water available
227 for evaporation [23].

228 The DOH is directly correlated to the amount of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, which can be calculated with the method
229 introduced by Wang et al. [24]. In this method, the mass loss in the temperature range 400-500°C
230 divided by the final mass at 1100°C is considered as the percentage of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$. Figure 11 presents
231 the $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ content as a function of BNP concentration at 7, 14 and 28 days. At 7 and 28 days,
232 the overall trend observed is that the amount of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ increases with increasing BNP
233 concentration. However, it is interesting to note that this trend is not evident at 14 days and this
234 needs to be investigated further. Overall, Fig. 11 suggests that the addition of BNP sheets
235 accelerates the hydration of cement, which results in the production of higher $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ contents at
236 7 and 28 days.

237 According Cao et al. [25], the HOD can be obtained by dividing the amount of the chemically
238 bound water (CBW) per unit gram of unhydrated cement by the CBW of fully hydrated cement
239 which is 0.23g. The CBW can be obtained by dividing the mass loss between 140 and 1100 °C by
240 the final mass [25]. Figure 12 shows the HOD as a function of BNP concentration at 7, 14 and 28
241 days. As can be seen from this figure, the results clearly show that the HOD increases with
242 increasing BPN concentration. For example, the DOH of the cement paste with 0.60-wt% BNPs
243 is increased with respect to the plain cement paste by 6%, 7%, and 9% at 7, 14 and 18 days,
244 respectively.

245 The improvement in the hydration of cement can be attributed to the effect of the BNP sheets on
246 the reaction of the cement particles with water. According to Cao et al. [25], hydrophilic additives
247 disperse well the cement particles during mixing thereby producing uniform distributions of the
248 cement particles which results in higher DOH. Furthermore, the hydrophilic BNP sheets tend to
249 store water molecules on their surface thus acting like internal water reservoirs thereby releasing
250 free water for further hydration. This additional hydration further increases the amount of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$
251 at 7 and 28 days. In addition, based on Cao et al. [25] hypothesis, the BNP sheets embedded into
252 the high density C-S-H could act as water channels and transfer water from the pore solution to
253 the un-hydrated cement cores, thus fueling the hydration of the cement particles [25].

254 *3.5. Influence of BNPs on the hydration phases of cementitious composites*

255 The XRD patterns of the cementitious composites at 7, 14 and 28 days are shown in Fig. 13. As
256 it can be seen from this figure, typical hydration phases such as ettringite, calcium hydroxide
257 $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, tricalcium silicate (C_3S) and (CaCO_3) are detected in all cementitious composites of all
258 ages. This indicates that the addition of BNP sheets does not alter the type and structure of the
259 hydration products of the cementitious. The C-S-H hydration phases are difficult to identify by

260 XRD analysis due to the lack of crystallinity and indefinite composition. As depicted, the intensity
261 of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ increases with increasing BNP concentration at 7, 14 and 28 days. This means the
262 addition of the BNP sheets promotes the hydration of cements thereby increasing the amount of
263 the hydration products, which is in line with the TGA results. Previous research on GO
264 cementitious composites also reported similar findings [24]. Another way to quantify the extent
265 of hydration of cement as a result of BNPs is to examine the magnitude of the intensity peaks of
266 the detected C_3S phase. From Fig. 13, it appears that the intensity peaks of C_3S decreases when
267 the BNP sheets are present. This could be attributed to the interaction of C_3S with $-\text{OH}$ and $-\text{R}-$
268 CH_2- functional groups on the surface of the BNP sheets. Phases such as C_3S tend to react with
269 water molecules adsorbed on the surface of the BNP sheets thereby increasing the amount of
270 hydration products.

271 Monitoring of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ crystal size could shed light on the effect of BNP on the growth of C-S-H
272 phases. The size of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ obtained from the XRD analysis as a function of BNP concentration
273 at 28 days is shown in Fig. 14. From this figure, it can be observed that the addition of BNP
274 significantly decreases the size of the $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ particles. This can be attributed to the fact that the
275 BNP sheets promote the growth of C-S-H, thus less space available for $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ to grow in size.
276 Zheng et al. [26] found that when GO is present in the matrix, the size of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ becomes smaller
277 and the content of C-S-H increases, resulting in a dense structure. It is noteworthy that the addition
278 of 0.40-wt% BNPs and 0.60 wt% BNPs leads to a $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ size higher than that at 0.2 wt BNPs.
279 This could be due to the fact that the BNP sheets tend to restack at higher concentrations which in
280 return dampers the grow of C-S-H and allows $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ to grow in size. Therefore, based on this
281 observation, it appears that the content of C-S-H reaches a maximum at 0.20-wt% BNPs at 28
282 days.

283 The EDX results were employed to further quantify the effect of the BNP sheets on the hydration
284 phases and their distribution in the cementitious composites. Here, the concentration of silica
285 signals are used as indication of C-S-H growth [27] whereas the concentration and uniformity of
286 the oxygen signals are used to gain insight into the distribution of the BNP sheets in the cement
287 matrix [28]. Figure 15 shows SEM images of the cementitious composites along with their
288 corresponding silica, oxygen and calcium maps at different BNP concentrations after 28 days of
289 curing. By comparing the silica maps between the cementitious composites, it is observed that the
290 composites with 0.20-wt% BNPs and 0.4-wt% BNPs exhibit higher silica concentration which
291 indicates higher C-S-H content. On the other hand, silica signals were not overserved in the
292 cementitious composite with 0.60 wt% BNPs, suggesting that $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ is the predominant phase,
293 but more work is needed to confirm this hypothesis. The comparison of the oxygen signals
294 indicates that the oxygen concentration is higher in the composites with 0.20-wt% BNPs and 0.40-
295 wt% BNPs and these oxygen signals are uniform throughout the maps, implying better distribution
296 of BNPs [28].

297 *3.6. Influence of BNP on the microstructure of cementitious composites*

298 The microstructure of the cementitious composites at 7, 14 and 28 days is presented in Figs.16-18.
299 As shown, the microstructure of the plain cementitious composite at 7 days (Fig. 16a) contains
300 unreacted cement particles as well as $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ cubes and seeds-like particles, presumably due to
301 a low DOH. The addition of 0.20-wt% BNPs leads to highly dense structure with some $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$
302 particles embedded into the C-S-H gel (Fig. 16b). The hydration phase $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ in the form of
303 cubes and rods-like crystals is observed in the microstructure of the composite with 0.40-wt%
304 BNPs (Fig. 16c). The cementitious composite with 0.60-wt% BNPs however, is marked by a high
305 content of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ seeds like crystals (Fig. 15d). It is worth to note that it is challenging to

306 identify the BNP sheets in the SEM images. This is because the hydration products such as
307 ettringite, $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and C-S-H grow on their surface thus making their morphology
308 undistinguishable.

309 From Figure 17a, it can be seen that the microstructure of the plain cementitious composite at 14
310 days becomes somewhat porous and contains a relatively high content of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ seeds-like
311 crystals, whereas the cementitious composite with 0.20-wt% BNPs (Fig. 17b) remains dense and
312 its C-S-H content seems to increase. The cementitious composite with 0.40-Wt% BNPs exhibits
313 a different morphology where the $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ seeds transformed into rods-like crystals and begin to
314 grow out from the matrix (Fig. 17c). As can be seen from Fig. 17d, when the BNP concentration
315 increases from 0.4-wt% BNPs to 0.6-wt% BNPs, the main hydration phase of the cementitious
316 composite is $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ in the form of agglomerates.

317 At 28 days of curing, the plain cementitious composite is mainly composed of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ in the form
318 of regular polyhedral shaped particles (18a). On the other hand, the cementitious composite with
319 0.20-wt% BNPs shows a compact structure with some layers of stacked fabrics-like $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$
320 crystals embedded into high density C-S-H gel (Figs. 18b-c). Most of these $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ fabrics
321 appear to grow in one-direction. This could be the result of the interaction of the uniformly
322 distributed BNP sheets with the cement particles. We hypothesized that when uniformly
323 distributed, the BNP sheets adsorb onto the surface of the cement particles through their -OH and
324 -R-CH₂- functional groups. These functional groups then react with C₃S and C₂S to form
325 nucleation and growth sites for the hydration phases. The phase C₂S is less soluble than C₃S, thus
326 a slower hydration rate of C₂S at these growth sites. At lower BNP concentrations, this could
327 allow more time for the hydration phases to self-assemble into fabric like-crystals. At a
328 concentration of 0.4-wt%, the cementitious composite contains C-S-H and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ as hydration

329 products. The $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ particles are in the form of elliptical needles growing out from the matrix
330 in two directions (Fig. 18d). When the BNP concentration increases to 0.6-wt% BNPs, $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$
331 is the main hydration product and the needle particles become cauliflower-like crystals as shown
332 in Figs. 18e-f. The SEM investigations suggest that the BNP sheets have the ability to regulate
333 the crystallization and morphology of the hydration products, which depends on the BNP
334 concentration in the cement matrix. The SEM investigations also suggest that the 0.20-wt% BNP
335 is the optimal concentration for increasing the C-S-H content in the cementitious composites.

336 The TEM images in Fig. 19 show the effect of BNP on the microstructure of the cementitious
337 composites at 28 days. As shown, the microstructure of the plain cementitious composite mainly
338 consists of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ crystals with a low C-S-H content. The addition of 0.2-wt% BNPs leads to
339 higher C-S-H content, fewer $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ crystals and denser microstructure (Fig. 19b). The TEM
340 image shown in Fig. 19c confirms the existence of fabric-like crystals in the cementitious
341 composite with 0.2-wt% BNPs. From Fig. 19d, the microstructure of the cementitious with 0.4-
342 wt% BNPs contains $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ crystals embedded into C-S-H gel. On the other hand, significant
343 amount of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ crystals is observed in the cementitious composite with 0.6-wt% BNPs.
344 Because of the hydroxyl functional groups on their surface, the BNP sheets are covalently bonded
345 to C-S-H and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ particles, thus making it challenging to identify them in the TEM images.

346 The TEM results further confirm the TGA, XRD, SEM and EDX findings that the BNP sheets
347 accelerate the hydration of cement thus increasing both C-S-H and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ contents in the
348 cementitious composites. The TEM results also confirm that the 0.20-wt% BNPs concentration
349 produces the highest C-S-H content.

350

351

352 3.7. Influence of BNP on the Mechanical properties of cementitious composites

353 The flexural strength (σ_c) and the modulus of elasticity (E_c) of the cement prisms were calculated
354 as [17]:

355
$$\sigma_c = \frac{3Pa}{b^3} \quad (2)$$

356
$$E_c = \frac{am(3l^2 - 4a^2)}{4b^4} \quad (3)$$

357 where l is the length of the prism between the supports, a is the distance between the support and
358 the loading point, P is the maximum applied load, b is the width and thickness of the prism and, m
359 is the slope of the tangent to the straight-line portion of the load–deflection curve.

360 The effect of BNP concentration on the average flexural strength of the cementitious composites
361 at 7, 14 and 28 days is given in Fig. 20. This figure shows that at 7 and 14 days, the addition of
362 0.20-wt% BNPs increases the flexural strength of the cementitious composites by 23% and 20%
363 respectively whereas, no significant increase is observed at 0.4-wt% BNPs and 0.6-wt% BNPs
364 concentrations. At 28 days, the flexural strength is increased by about 80% and 50% at BNP
365 concentrations of 0.20-wt% and 0.40-wt%, respectively. This increase however, significantly
366 diminishes at 0.60-wt% BNPs.

367 Figure 21 presents the average modulus of elasticity of the cementitious composites as a function
368 of BNP concentration at 28 days. As depicted, the modulus of elasticity follows a similar trend to
369 that of the flexural strength at 28 days. A significant modulus of elasticity gain of about 200% is
370 achieved at BNP concentration of 0.20-wt%. However, like the flexural strength, the modulus of
371 elasticity diminishes at higher BNP concentrations.

372 The percentage increase in the mechanical properties of the cementitious composites diminishes
373 at BNP concentrations higher than 0.20-wt%, probably because of the synergetic effect of the

374 restacking of the BNP sheets and the high content of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ crystals. We hypothesize that at
375 higher BNP concentrations, severe restacking of the BNP sheets occurs in the high alkaline cement
376 pastes, thereby reducing their mechanical properties. The high alkaline cement pore solution rich
377 in Ca^{2+} ions attenuates the hydroxyl groups on the surface of the BNP sheets and high van-der-
378 Waals forces are created, thereby allowing the sheets to stack on top of each other to form stiff
379 agglomerates [17]. These agglomerates weaken the matrix, causing the cement composites to fail
380 in a brittle manner with lower mechanical properties. The high content of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ crystals in the
381 cementitious composites containing 0.40-wt% BNPs and 0.60-wt% BNPs could also diminish the
382 mechanical properties. $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ crystals are typically brittle in nature thereby weakening the
383 cement matrix by making it highly susceptible to a brittle fracture. Based on this, 0.20-wt% BNPs
384 is the optimal content for maximum mechanical properties.

385 *3.8. Interaction mechanism between BNP and cement matrix*

386 The improvement of the mechanical properties of the cementitious composites containing 0.20-
387 wt% BNPs and 0.40-wt% BNPs can be attributed both to improved hydration kinetics of the
388 cement particles which results in higher C-S-H content and the reinforcing effect of the BNP
389 sheets. The reinforcing effect is controlled by the mechanical interaction between the BNP sheets
390 and the cementitious matrix coupled with chemical cross-linking type bonding. As showing in
391 Fig. 6b, the BNP sheets are characterized by a wrinkled texture. This morphology plays a
392 significant role in the toughening and load transfer mechanisms in the cementitious composites,
393 because it enhances the mechanical interlocking [17]. Saafi et al. [17] have shown that the
394 mechanical interaction between the BNP sheets and the cement matrix can be examined using both
395 the morphology of the BNP sheets and the shear lag model. The strain ϵ_p in the BNP sheet as a
396 function of the strain ϵ_m in the cement matrix is [29]:

397
$$\varepsilon_p = \varepsilon_m \left[1 - \frac{\cosh\left(\frac{nsx}{l}\right)}{\cosh\left(\frac{ns}{l}\right)} \right] \quad (4)$$

398
$$n = \sqrt{\frac{2G_m t}{E_p T}}$$

399 where s is the aspect ratio of the BNP sheet (l/t), n represents the interfacial stress transfer
 400 efficiency and the product ns represents both the morphology of the BNP sheet and the degree of
 401 interaction with the cementitious material. G_m is the shear modulus of the cementitious material,
 402 t is the thickness of the BNP sheet, T is the total thickness of the cementitious material, E_p is the
 403 modulus elasticity of the BNP sheet and l is the length of the BNP sheet in the x direction [29].
 404 The mechanical interaction between the two materials is slowly depending on the morphology of
 405 the BNP sheet (Fig. 6b) which can be characterized by the wavelength λ and the amplitude A of
 406 the wrinkles and ribs as [30]:

407
$$\lambda^4 = \frac{4\pi^2 \nu (tl)^2}{3(1-\nu^2)\varepsilon} \quad (5)$$

408
$$A^2 = \left[\frac{16\varepsilon\nu}{3\pi^2(1-\nu^2)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} tl \quad (6)$$

409 where ε is the compressive strain in the BNP sheet resulting from the chemical treatment, ν is the
 410 Poisson's ratio of the BNP sheet. The shear stress τ between the BNP sheet and the matrix in the
 411 direction x is [29]:

412
$$\tau = nE_p \varepsilon_m \frac{\sinh\left(\frac{nsx}{l}\right)}{\cosh\left(\frac{ns}{2}\right)} \quad (7)$$

413 Equations (4), (5), (6) and (7) indicate that the observed increase in the mechanical properties of
 414 the BNP cementitious composites at 0.20-wt% BNPs and 0.40-wt% BNPs is in part as a result of

415 a good mechanical interaction between the two materials which is controlled by properties of the
416 BNP sheets mainly the high aspect ratio, the modulus of elasticity and the surface morphology.
417 The BNP characterization results indicate that the BNP sheets are fully decorated with hydroxyl
418 functional groups which are responsible for their high chemical reactivity. These functional
419 groups are believed to adsorb on the surface of the cement particles. In this case, the main chemical
420 components of the cement C_2S and C_3S hydrate over the surface of the BNP sheets, leading to
421 intercalated C-S-H/BNP and $Ca(OH)_2$ /BNP particles. Figure 22 shows the chemical interaction
422 of the BNP sheets with C-S-H. The strong interfacial covalent bonding between C-S-H and the
423 functionalized BNP sheets enhances the stress transfer thus improving the overall mechanical
424 properties of the cementitious composites at BNP concentrations of 0.20-wt% and 0.40-wt%.

425 *3.9. Influence of BNP on the Fracture properties of cementitious composites: numerical simulation* 426 *and experimental results*

427 The three-point-bending fracture tests were numerically simulated by ABAQUS to further
428 elucidate their fracture behavior and validate the experimental results. In order to capture the
429 evolution of cracks, extended finite element method (X-FEM) was used as the finite element mesh
430 need not conform to the varying internal boundaries caused by the propagation of cracks. Hence,
431 a single mesh is sufficient for completing entire simulation of a test. Fig.23 shows the geometry
432 of the X-FEM model for the cement prism with and without BNP. The dimensions of the prisms
433 are identical to the ones used in the laboratory tests. The prisms are simply supported near the two
434 ends. The force is applied at the mid-span, where a 16mm long virtual crack perpendicular to the
435 bottom surface is embedded. The prisms were discretized by cubic C3D8R elements. Mesh
436 sensitivity analysis was carried out and it was found that elements of $2\text{mm}\times 2\text{mm}\times 2\text{mm}$ were
437 sufficiently small to achieve converged results. The maximum principal stress fracture criteria

438 was used to initiate fracture. The material properties of the cementitious composites of the XFEM
439 models were taken from the laboratory tests described in Sections 3.7 and 3.8 and, the details are
440 shown in Table 2.

441 Figure 24 shows the predicted and measured load vs CMOD response plain prisms and prisms
442 with 0.20-wt% BNPs (optimal BNP concentration). It is worth mentioning that it was not possible
443 to experimentally capture the post-cracking response of the prisms due to the limitation of the test
444 machine employed in this investigation. As shown, at the optimal BNP concentration, the fracture
445 load, stiffness and the amount of absorbed energy are significantly increased, thus better fracture
446 properties. Figure 24 shows that the FEM model provides a good prediction of the fracture load
447 of the prisms, though it overestimates their stiffness.

448 The experimental fracture energy G_f and the fracture toughness K_{IC} were calculated according to
449 [31]: The calculated average G_f and K_{IC} are about 12.55 Nm/m^2 , $0.16 \text{ MPa m}^{0.5}$, respectively, for
450 the plain prism, and 23.61 Nm/m^2 and $0.33 \text{ MPa m}^{0.5}$ respectively, for the prism containing 0.20-
451 wt% BNPs. This shows that the addition of BNPs increases G_f and K_{IC} by about 88% and 106%,
452 respectively.

453 Figure 25 compares the observed and simulated cracking behavior of the prisms. As shown, there
454 is a good agreement between both the simulated and experimental failure mode of the prisms. The
455 failure mode of the plain cement prism is Mode I crack propagation along the surface of the initial
456 notch. The failure mode of the prism containing 0.20-wt% BNPs is somewhat mixed mode (Mode
457 I+II) crack propagation in the form of an inclined crack initiated slightly above the notch tip. This
458 can be attributed to the BNP crack deflection effect and the improved flexural strength.

459 The significant increase in the fracture properties of the BNP cementitious composites is attributed
460 to the toughening mechanisms originated from the presence of BNP sheets. As shown in Fig. 26b,

461 the toughness seems to be governed by the crack-bridging mechanism where the BNP sheet
462 appears to disentangle into nanofibers under stress and bridge the crack. Figures 26c and 26d show
463 another toughening mechanism associated with mainly crack deflection that bypasses the BNP
464 sheet at the BNP/matrix interface.

465 **Conclusions**

466 In this paper, we demonstrate for the first time that nanoplatelets synthesized from food waste such
467 as sugar beetroot can be used as a low-cost and renewable reinforcing material in cementitious
468 materials. The proposed BNP sheets exhibit some characteristics of GO such as hydrophilic
469 functional groups, high specific area and good dispersibility in water. An integrated experimental
470 and numerical simulation approach was employed to evaluate the performance of cementitious
471 composites containing BNP sheets.

472 Because of their high surface area and hydrophilicity, the BNP sheets tend to consume water
473 thereby reducing the workability of the cement pastes at BNP concentrations higher than 0.20-
474 wt%. The incorporation of the BNP sheets increased the degree of hydration of cement due to the
475 active participation of their functional groups and their supply of water molecules, resulting in
476 high content of the hydration products. The microstructure, the type of the hydration phases and
477 the mechanical properties seemed to be highly dependent on the amount of the BNP sheets.
478 Compared to the plain cementitious composite, the cementitious composite with 0.20-wt% BNPs
479 showed denser microstructure with C-S-H as the main hydration phase. At higher BNP
480 concentrations, Ca(OH)_2 was the main hydration phase. The BNP sheets appeared to regulate the
481 morphology of Ca(OH)_2 crystals. At 28 days, the regular polyhedral shaped Ca(OH)_2 particles in
482 the plain cementitious composite changed to stacked fabric-like Ca(OH)_2 at 0.20-wt% BNPs,
483 elliptical needles at 0.40-wt% BNPs and cauliflower-like Ca(OH)_2 at 0.60-wt%.

484 The experimental results suggested that 0.20-wt% BNPs is the optimal concentration for maximum
485 amount of C-S-H gel and mechanical properties. At this BNP content, the flexural strength and
486 the modulus of elasticity were by increased by 80% and 200%, respectively. Both experimental
487 and numerical simulation results showed that the fracture resistance of the cementitious
488 composites were significantly improved at 0.20-wt% BNPs due to the crack bridging and crack
489 deflection effects of the BNP sheets. At this concentration, the fracture energy and the fracture
490 toughness were increased by about 88% and 106%, respectively.

491 Although further studies are required to investigate the durability of the proposed cementitious
492 composites and optimize their properties, the proposed 2D BNP has the potential to create durable
493 and high performance cementitious materials with low-embodied carbon for various applications
494 in the construction sector.

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Fig. 1. Test details of the prisms and schematic of test setups. a) flexural strength test setup, b) fracture test setup (not to scale).

Fig. 2. Images of the experimental test setups. a) flexural strength test setup, b) notched prism with optical grid for fracture test., c) fracture test setup with digital camera for CMOD measurement, d) close up view of the notched prism under load.

Table 1: Chemicals composition of the BNP sheets

Chemical components	C	O	Ca	Al	Cl	Mg	Si	Na
Content (%)	47.61	46.91	1.86	1.81	0.67	0.57	0.40	0.17

Fig. 3. XRD spectrum of the BNP sheets showing crystalline region at $2\theta = 15$ and amorphous/crystalline regions at $2\theta = 22.5$.

Fig. 4. Diffuse FTIR spectra of the BNP sheets used to determine the their functional groups

Fig. 5: Thermal stability of the BNP sheets showing TGA and DTA curves

Fig. 6. SEM image showing the surface morphology of the BNP sheets.

Fig. 7: a) BNP aqueous solution (2g/L) after 30 min of sonication, b) optical image of the BNP aqueous solution.

Fig.8. UV-vis spectroscopy results of BNP aqueous solutions at different sonication times

Fig. 9. Effect of the BNP sheets on the workability of the cement paste

Fig. 10: TGA curves (a) and DTA curves (b) for the cementitious composites at BNP concentrations of 0 (control), 0.2, 0.4 and 0.6-wt% at 28 days.

Fig. 11: Content of calcium hydroxide obtained from TGA as a function of BNP concentration at 7, 14 and 28 days

Fig. 12. Degree of hydration (DOH) of the cementitious composites obtained from TGA as a function of BNP concentration at 7, 14 and 28 days.

Fig. 13. XRD spectrum of the cementitious composites at different BNP concentrations, a) 7 days, b) 14 days, c) at 28 days. C-S-H: Calcium Silicate hydrate. E: Ettringite, P: Portlandite ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$), A: Alite (C_3S), C: Calcite (CaCO_3).

Fig. 14. Size of Ca(OH)₂ obtained from XRD as a function of BNP concentration

Fig. 15. SEM images with maps of silica, oxygen and calcium elements at 28 days of curing. a) plain cementitious composite, b) with 0.20-wt% BNPs, c) with 0.40-wt% BNPs, d) with 0.60-wt% BNPs

Fig.16. SEM micro images of the cementitious composites at 7 days. a) plain cementitious composite, b) with 0.20-wt% BNPs, c) with 0.40-wt% BNPs, d) with 0.60-wt% BNPs

Fig.17. SEM micro images of the cementitious composites at 14 days. a) plain cementitious composite, b) with 0.20-wt% BNPs, c) with 0.40-wt% BNPs, d) with 0.60-wt% BNPs

Fig.18. SEM micro images of the cementitious composites at 28 days. a) plain cementitious composite, b,c) with 0.20-wt% BNPs, d) with 0.40-wt% of BNPs, e,f) with 0.60-wt% of BNPs

Fig. 19. TEM micro images at 28 days of curing a) plain cementitious composite, b,c) with 0. 20-wt% BNPs, c) with 0. 20-wt% BNPs showing fabrics-like crystals, d) with 0.40-wt% BNPs, e) with 0.60-wt% BNPs

Fig. 20. Variation of the flexural strength as a function of BNP concentration at different curing ages

Figure 21. Variation of the modulus of elasticity as a function of BNP concentration at 28 days

Fig. 22. Schematic illustration of intermolecular interaction of BPN with C-S-H phase

Fig. 23. X-FEM model of the notched cementitious composite prism for fracture modelling and analysis

Table 2. Average material properties of the cementitious composites

Material	Flexural strength (MPa)	Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)	Fracture Energy (N/M)
Plain cement	1.2	1.12	12.55
With 0.20-wt% BNPs	2.1	3.25	23.60

Fig. 24. Load versus crack mouth opening displacement for cementitious composites with and without BNPs. experimental versus modelling.

Figure 25. Experimental and simulated fracture behavior of the cementitious composite beams. a) plain cement prism, b) with 0.20-wt% BNPs.

Fig. 26. SEM micro image showing crack propagation in a) plain cementitious composite, b) with BNPs showing BNP crack bridging, c and d) with BNP showing crack deflection